

THREE-DIMENSIONAL PRINTING OF CONTINUOUS CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS BY IN-NOZZLE IMPREGNATION WITH COMPACTION ROLLER

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ABSTRACT

3D printing technique for continuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) has been developed based on fusion deposition modeling (FDM). The technique enables direct 3D fabrication without the use of molds. A thermoplastic filament and continuous carbon fibers were separately supplied to the 3D printer and continuous carbon fibers were impregnated with the thermoplastic resin within the heated nozzle immediately before printing. Compaction roller was equipped with the printer head to consolidate 3D printed CFRTP.

In this study, Polylactic acid (PLA) was used as a matrix material, and carbon fibers were used as a reinforcement material. The test specimens were printed as the fibers were aligned to loading direction. The tensile and bending tests are performed to investigate the mechanical properties of the 3D printed unidirectional CFRTP specimens. The tensile and bending tests results of the unidirectional CFRTP specimens showed improved mechanical properties by compaction in the printing process.

1 INTRODUCTION

3D printing enables fabrication of near-net-shape complex three-dimensional parts without expensive molds or tools if one only has 3D CAD data [1-3]. Although there are several types of 3D printing systems, fused deposition modeling technique based 3D printer has been widely used because of the simple structure and usability. However, the mechanical properties of products fabricated by conventional 3D printer were inherently low because it usually uses thermoplastic resins for the material although process parameter optimizations such as laminating direction and laminate thickness were investigated for improving the mechanical properties. Thus, the 3D printer was usually used for rapid prototyping, and it cannot be applied to manufacturing of structural components that can be used in aerospace or automobile industries.

To improve the mechanical properties of a 3D printed part, the 3D printer that fabricates continuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) is highly demanded [4-5]. 3D printer that prints continuous CFRTP could reduce weight by optimizing the fiber direction in the components. This technology is highly suitable for manufacturing of a wide variety of products in small quantities, e.g. in the health-care industries such as load-bearing orthopedic implants and artificial legs in addition to the automobile and aerospace industries.

In this study, 3D printing technique of continuous CFRTP was developed based on fused deposition modeling. In this process, the selection of any resins and reinforced fibers for 3D printing is possible. A thermoplastic filament and continuous carbon fibers were separately supplied to the 3D printer, and fibers were impregnated with a filament in the heated nozzle just before printing. Compaction roller was equipped with the printer head to consolidate continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics just after printing.

For demonstration, a 1K straight tow of carbon fibers was used for reinforcement whereas PLA resin was used for matrix. Impregnation process is important in this 3D printer to obtain fully impregnated CFRTP. Drawing speed and nozzle temperature were parametrically studied. If the drawing speed was high or nozzle temperature was low, un-impregnated CFRTP was printed. On the

other hands, fully impregnated CFRP was obtained if the condition was selected properly. Then, unidirectional CFRTP specimens for tensile test and bending test were printed. The tensile and bending test results showed improved mechanical properties of the unidirectional CFRTP specimens by compaction in the 3D printing process.

2 FABRICATION AND TESTING METHOD

2.1 3D printing of a continuous CFRTP by in-nozzle impregnation

The 3D printer for continuous CFRTP was developed by modifying the printer head of a commercially available FDM 3D printer. Figure 1 shows the 3D printer head. A thermoplastic resin filament and a continuous carbon fiber tow are separately supplied to the printer head. The resin filament is supplied using a stepping motor, while the continuous carbon fiber tow is directly inserted into the nozzle and drawn by the compaction roller equipped with the nozzle head. The thermoplastic resin filament is melted in the heated nozzle, and consolidated with the continuous carbon fiber tow. The nozzle has a tapered hole inside and the outlet diameter was 0.4 mm. The continuous CFRTP is extruded from the nozzle and laminated onto heated table by pressing with compaction roller for the layer-by-layer fabrication. The compaction roller reduces internal voids of printed CFRTP by compaction force [6]. Compaction roller also makes smooth surface of printed CFRTP and prevents peeling of printed CFRTP from the heated table.

2.2 Materials and printing condition

For demonstration, straight tow of carbon fibers (1K, T300B, Toray) was used for reinforcement and poly-lactic acid (PLA) was used for matrix resin. Impregnation process is important in the 3D printer to obtain fully impregnated CFRTP. Drawing speed and nozzle temperature were parametrically studied. In this study, the impregnation length was determined to 65 mm while drawing speed was changed as 100, 200, 300 mm/min and nozzle temperature as 210, 230, 250 °C. Totally 9 printing conditions were studied.

Table 1 showed the experimental results. If the drawing speed was high or nozzle temperature was low, un-impregnated CFRTP were printed, and the cross-section was shown in Figure 2(a). On the other hands, fully impregnation condition was obtained if the conditions were selected properly, and

(a) Schematic diagram

(b) Printing of unidirectional CFRTP

Figure 1: The nozzle head with compaction roller.

		Nozzle temperature [°C]		
		210	230	250
Drawing speed [mm/min]	100	OK	OK	OK
	200	OK	OK	OK
	300	NG	NG	NG

Table 1: Test conditions for impregnation process.

the cross-section was shown in Figure 2(b). Based on the results, the drawing speed of 200 mm/min and the nozzle temperature of 250 °C were selected in the following.

2.3 3D printing of test specimens

Tensile and bending tests were conducted to evaluate the mechanical property of a 3D printed CFRTP. The tensile and bending test specimens were printed as the fibers were aligned to loading direction. Both specimens were rectangular coupon. Dimensions of the tensile test specimen was $100 \times 10 \times 1$ mm, and bending test specimen was $100 \times 15 \times 2$ mm. Neat PLA specimen was also printed for comparison. Figure 3 shows a 3D printed unidirectional CFRTP for bending test. Two types of CFRTP specimen were printed with compaction (Compacted CFRTP) or without compaction (Non-compacted CFRTP) for both tensile and bending specimens. For printing of neat PLA specimen (Neat-PLA), the compaction roller was not used. Three specimens were prepared and tested respectively. Fiber volume fraction (V_f) of the 3D printed CFRTP was determined by the supplied amounts of carbon fibers and weight of the 3D printed composite, and it was about 30 %.

2.4 Tensile and bending test methods

Tensile and bending tests were conducted using universal testing machine (AG-IS 150kN, Shimadzu Corporation) as shown in Figure 4(a) for tensile test and 4(b) for three-point bending test. The tests were conducted at a loading speed of 0.5 mm/min. Strain was measured by a strain gauge attached onto the central of the specimen.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Tensile test results

Tensile stress and tensile strain relations of the compacted CFRTP, non-compacted CFRTP and neat PLA specimens were shown in Figure 5. The tensile modulus and tensile strength are summarized in Table 2. The tensile modulus and strength of non-compacted CFRTP were increased 1389 % and 1356 % of those of neat-PLA specimen respectively. The tensile modulus and strength of compacted CFRTP were further increased more than 30 % of those of non-compacted CFRTP. Compaction force increased mechanical property of the 3D printed CFRTP.

Figure 2: Cross-sectional observation of 3D printed CFRTP.

Figure 3: A 3D printed CFRTP specimen for bending test.

(a) Tensile test.

(b) Three-point bending test.

Figure 4: Tensile test and bending test of the 3D printed unidirectional CFRTP specimen.

Figure 5: A typical example of tensile stress-tensile strain curves.

Figure 6: A typical example of bending stress-bending strain curves.

	Tensile test		Bending test	
	Strength [MPa]	Modulus [GPa]	Strength [MPa]	Modulus [GPa]
Compacted CFRTP	536 ± 72.8	63.9 ± 6.10	222 ± 89.1	24.0 ± 5.47
Non-compacted CFRTP	393 ± 10.7	49.1 ± 0.437	157 ± 64.9	25.1 ± 2.56
Neat-PLA	39.5 ± 1.44	4.66 ± 0.253	64.9 ± 1.32	2.49 ± 0.0984
Compacted CFRTP + Hot pressing			841	58.4

Table 2: Tensile and bending test results.

3.2 Bending test results

Bending stress and bending strain relations of the compacted CFRTP, non-compacted CFRTP and neat PLA specimens were shown in Figure 6. The bending modulus and bending strength are summarized in Table 2. The bending modulus and strength of non-compacted CFRTP were increased 1012 % and 242 % of those of neat-PLA specimen. However, bending modulus and strength were much lower than the tensile modulus and strength. This may attribute the weak interfacial bonding, and discussed later. The bending strength of compacted CFRTP was further increased more than 40 %

of that of non-compacted CF RTP specimen. However, bending modulus was not improved by compaction force.

3.3 Cross-sectional observation

Cross sections for compacted and non-compacted CF RTP were shown in Figure 7. The non-compacted CF RTP has an elliptical shape while the compacted CF RTP has a flat shape. For the non-compacted CF RTP, relatively large voids were developed between adjacent filaments. The voids were decreased in the compacted CF RTP as compared to the non-compacted CF RTP. Tensile property of the 3D printed CF RTP was improved by reducing the gap between the filaments and promoting the load transfer between adjacent filaments allowing the filaments to carry the load.

3.4 Failure mode

The tensile specimens of compacted and non-compacted CF RTP were separated into two at the gage section after the tensile tests. This indicated that tensile load was effectively transferred to the whole filaments. By contrast, delamination was developed in bending test for both compacted and non-compacted bending specimens (Figure 8), and the specimens were not separated after bending test. Delamination in bending test indicated low interfacial adhesion between filaments. Compaction roller increased bending strength although the failure mode was still unchanged.

3.5 Effect of postprocessing on mechanical property of the 3D printed CF RTP

In the bending test, delamination was developed and the resultant bending property was lower than the tensile property. Low interfacial bonding may attribute the lower bending property although the compaction force was applied in the printing process. Therefore, hot-pressing was applied for the specimens as a postprocess to improve interfacial bonding between filaments.

Compacted CF RTP specimens were postprocessed at 180 °C for 1 hour under pressure using a hot-press machine. After the postprocess, the specimens were supplied for three-point bending test. Figure 9 shows the bending stress-bending strain curves for compacted CF RTP specimens with and without postprocess. The bending property was summarized in Table 2. The bending modulus was improved and it was close to the tensile modulus. Although compaction force was applied to 3D printed CF RTP, load transfer between each filament was not sufficient inside the specimen. In the tensile test, tensile load was applied at the tabs on both end of the tensile specimen by wedge grips of the universal testing machine, which applied tensile load to almost all filament. However, in the

(a) With compaction roller.

(b) Without compaction roller.

Figure 7 Cross-sections observation of 3D printed CF RTP (a single filament).

Figure 8: Bending failure of the 3D printed CF RTP specimen.

Figure 9: Bending stress-bending strain curves after postprocess.

bending test, shear load should be transferred in the specimen to withstand bending moment. Low load-transfer efficiency between filaments resulted in low bending modulus. Low interfacial bonding also resulted in the low bending strength.

4 CONCLUSIONS

3D printing technique of a continuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics was experimentally studied. A thermoplastic filament and continuous carbon fibers were separately supplied to the 3D printer and fibers were impregnated with resin within the heated nozzle. Compaction roller was equipped with the printer head to consolidate printed material. Tensile and bending tests are performed to investigate the mechanical properties of the 3D printed continuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic. The results obtained in this paper were summarized as follows.

- (1) In-nozzle impregnation condition was studied, and fully impregnation condition was obtained. Mechanical properties of the 3D printed CF RTP specimens were greatly improved compared with the neat-resin specimen.
- (2) The gaps between adjacent filaments were reduced by compaction force. Tensile property and bending property of the 3D printed CF RTP specimens were further improved by compaction in the 3D printing process.
- (3) Delamination was developed in bending test of the 3D printed CF RTP specimen. Low load-transfer efficiency between filaments resulted in lower bending property than the tensile property. Printing condition needs to be optimized to improve the interfacial bonding.

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